

Bohm's Formalism, Bound States and Component Plane Waves

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March, 20, 2019

Recently, there have been numerous articles in the literature dealing with Bohm's formulation of quantum mechanics obtained by writing the wavefunction $W(x)$ in polar complex notation, namely $R(x,t)\exp(iS(x,t))$. In general, however, this approach has been applied to time dependent quantum mechanics. Reducing the result to the time independent case, yields the usual time-independent Schrodinger equation, but the current in Bohm's approach disappears. In this note, we try to see if the Bohm formalism may be used to obtain information about the quantum bound state and its relationship to plane waves. Traditionally, this relationship is based on the wavefunction being written as a Fourier transform $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ip)$ with the $\exp(ip)$ being identified as plane waves. By examining the Bohm formalism, it seems one can see the transformation of $\exp(ikx-Et)$, $\exp(-ikx-iEt)$ plane waves for which an $S(x,t)$ exists, to the case where the plane waves combine to yield only $R(x)$ (with respect to x), leaving only $\exp(iEt)$ for $\exp(iS)$. More importantly, one may try to see how quantum mechanics is based on a constant energy density $EW(x)W(x)$ at each point x , while classical statistical mechanics is based on constant temperature at each point. For the ground state of an oscillator, the time-independent Schrodinger equation seems to become an equation of free energy equaling $EW(x)W(x)$, with kinetic energy representing energy in the free energy expression. This helps to link quantum mechanics and classical statistical mechanics as two different statistical models which become similar in the ground state oscillator case.

The Bohm Formalism

In (1), the Bohm formalism is established by writing the wavefunction in polar complex form, namely:

$$W(x) = R(x,t) \exp[iS(x,t)] \quad ((1))$$

It should be noted that in the bound state case one has $R(x,t)=R(x)$ and $\exp(iS(x,t))=\exp(iEt)$. If $S(x,t)$ has spatial dependence, then it seems to be related to momentum flux, but there can still be flux in the bound state case, (it seems). To get a sense of this, consider a particle in a box with no potential. Then $W(x)=C \sin(kx) = C/2i[\exp(ikx)-\exp(-ikx)]$. In other words, two terms $\exp(ikx-Et)/2i$ and $\exp(-kx-Et)/2i$, each with $S(x,t)$, combine to form a real function $\sin(kx)$, shifting the x dependence from $S(x,t)$ to $R(x)$, but any physical current may still be present. This idea will help show how $R(x)$ is built up from plane waves $\exp(ikx-Et)$. First, however, consider using ((1)) in the time dependent Schrodinger equation. This leads to two equations:

$$-R(x,t) \frac{d}{dt} S(x,t) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} R(x,t) + V(x) R(x,t) - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\frac{d}{dx} S(x,t) \right]^2 \quad ((2))$$

and

$$d/dt R(x,t) = -\hbar^2/2m [2d/dx R(x,t) d/dx S(x,t) + R d/dx d/dx S(x,t)] \quad ((3))$$

One may see that if $S(x,t)=Et$ then ((2)) becomes the time independent Schrodinger equation and ((3)) vanishes. ((3)) is often written as a conservation of probability equation:

$$d/dt W(x,t)W(x,t) + d/dx [W(x,t)W(x,t) d/dx S(x,t)] = 0 \text{ with } W(x,t)W(x,t)=R(x,t)R(x,t)$$

The Bohm formalism [((2)) and ((3))] seems to apply to the time dependent case with $d/dx S(x,t)$ representing a momentum flux. As mentioned, however, $\exp(ikx-iEt)$ and $\exp(-ikx -iEt)$, which separately fit this Bohm time-dependent scheme, can combine to create $\exp(iEt) \sin(kx)$. Now, the entire spatial dependence is contained in $R(x)$ while for the plane waves, $R(x)$ was constant. In the plane wave case, a separate flux $d/dx S(x,t)$ for $\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(-ikx)$ existed. It seems this physical flux may also be present in the bound state, even though it seems to cancel "out". This is important as it may help one picture creating a bound state from plane waves.

To begin, one may note that in the case of $V(x)=0$, one has only $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ and $\exp(-ipx-Et)$ with $E=p^2/2m$. One may try to generalize to a case with a nonzero $V(x)$ and:

$$W(x,t)= \text{Sum over } p \quad f_p \exp(ipx - iE(p)t) \text{ with } E(p)= p^2/2m \quad ((4))$$

In such a case, there will be an $S(x,t)$, which means there will be an overall momentum flux $d/dx S(x,t)$. This may not represent equilibrium. It might be good to have $S(t)$ only, in other words $S(t)= E_{total} t$. In such a case, all x dependence shifts to $R(x)$ with pairs $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ combining to form real functions $\sin(px)$ with weights f_p . These must balance $V(x)$ so that all x dependence becomes proportional to $R(x)$ as shown in equation ((2)). This differs from classical statistical mechanics in which plane waves $\exp(ipx)$ with weight f_p combine to form a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ regardless of the potential $V(x)$. The potential changes the density, but not f_p . In quantum mechanics, $V(x)$ changes f_p .

Thus, the Bohm approach seems to show how plane waves can combine to form real functions $\sin(px)$ which shift spatial dependence from $S(x,t)$ to $R(x)$, creating a bound state in this manner with possible hidden flux included. If one examines equation ((3)), the loss of spatial dependence in $S(x,t)$ immediately leads to a flux $d/dx S(x,t)=0$ and yields zero for the right hand side of the equation. This, however, is linked to $d/dt R(x,t)=0$ or a constant density $R(x)R(x)$. That does not mean that there cannot be underlying currents. For example, $d/dx R(x)R(x)=2 R(x)d/dx R(x)$. Here $[d/dx R(x)]/R(x)$ appears to be proportional to a velocity as:

$$[d/dx R(x)]/R(x) = [\text{Sum over } p \quad f_p \cos(px)] / R(x) \text{ where } R(x)= \text{Sum over } p \quad f_p \sin(px) \quad ((4))$$

In a previous set of notes (2), the role of this flux in the time-independent Schrodinger equation has been considered. It should be noted that in ((4)), the traditional approach of using Fourier transforms is applied to try to see the "plane waves" within the bound state. With Bohm formalism, this relationship seems to occur by shifting from a spatial $S(x,t)$ to a spatial $R(x)$.

It is interesting to note that in the expression for flux ((4)), one has $R(x)$ in the denominator. In the case of $V(x)=0$, i.e. a particle in a box, $R(x)=C\sin(kx)=C/2[\exp(ikx) - \exp(-ikx)]$. Thus, although the numerator $d/dx R(x)$ looks similar to the sum of the flux in the Bohm case for each plane wave considered separately i.e. $ik = [d/dx \exp(ikx)]/\exp(ikx)$ and a similar expression for $-ikx$, the factor $R(x)$ in the denominator of ((4)) is different. A similar argument can be made for the calculation of kinetic energy. For a plane wave it is: $(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx \exp(ikx)]/\exp(ikx) = (1/2m) k^2$. For a full wavefunction, the form stays the same, namely:

$$[(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx R(x)]/R(x) \quad ((4.5))$$

But with $R(x)$ in the denominator, one can see this is no longer the sum of kinetic energy terms of the individual plane waves. From ((2)), one sees that kinetic energy of a plane wave is contained in the term proportional to $[d/dx S(x,t)]^2$, but shifts to the term proportional to $[d/dx d/dx R(x)]/R(x)$ for a bound state. This is an important point, because in (4) it was argued that $R(x)$ in the denominator of ((4.5)) represents a normalization constant associated with a conditional probability $P(p/x)$. Equation ((2)) shows how one moves from $(-1/2m) [d/dx S]^2$ to $(-1/2m) (1/R) (d/dx d/dx R)$, thus changing from a local kinetic energy to a conditional probability picture.

It is also interesting to note the changes in entropy that occur as one converts from free plane waves with $S(x,t)$ to $S(t)$ and $R(x)$. The entropy of $\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(-ikx)$ separately is zero if one uses the definition $S \text{ density} = -k \text{ density} \ln(\text{density})$ as density for $\exp(ikx) = \exp(ikx) * \exp(-ikx)$. When the two combine, there is uncertainty as one does not know if a particle is moving forward or backwards, so $S \text{ density} = -k \sin(kx)\sin(kx)/2 \ln[\sin(kx)]$ and there is entropy.

Ground State of an Oscillator and Free Energy

In the above section, it was argued that plane waves with weight f_p combined to "combat" the potential in order to create $E R(x)$ which is proportional to $E R(x)R(x)$ or $E \text{ density}(x)$. Thus, the statistical constraint behind quantum mechanics seems to be the assurance of an energy density proportional to density:

$$E(x,t) = E R(x)R(x) \quad ((5))$$

In classical statistical mechanics, one enforces a constant temperature everywhere and for the ideal gas law has:

$$P(x,t) = \text{density}(x,t) T \quad \text{even for cases in fluid mechanics}$$

For the ground state of an oscillator, however, quantum mechanics and classical statistical mechanics become the same in form. It is interesting to note that for such a case:

$V(x) R(x)R(x) = C \text{ density}(x) \ln[\text{density}(x)]$ i.e. the potential multiplied by density is proportional to Shannon's entropy. In an earlier note, it was argued that the Schrodinger equation was equivalent in this case to maximizing entropy. This is in keeping with the ideas of statistical mechanics and shows how quantum mechanics seems to match classical statistical mechanics for this special case. For other cases, the constraint ((5)) destroys this relationship and forces different f_p values.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, due to the high frequency in which the Bohm formalism appears in recent literature and due to its inclusion of a flux $d/dxS(x,t)$, it was decided to see if this formalism could be applied to bound states for which $S(x,t)=S(t)$. In such a case, the flux would formally disappear, but it was seen that $\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(-ikx)$ pairs which separately have flux and $S(x,t)$ could combine to form a real function $\sin(kx)$ and thus shift x dependence from $S(x,t)$ to $R(x)$. It seems that this allows one to see how plane wave pairs come together to create an $R(x)$ function which counteracts the potential $V(x)$ in order to produce an $ER(x)$ where E is total energy. It is argued that having energy density = E density is the underlying statistical constraint in bound state quantum mechanics, unlike the constraint of constant temperature in classical statistical mechanics. For the ground state quantum oscillator, the two approaches coincide and the two different statistical mechanical models become largely the same.

References

1. Budiyni, Agung and Umeno, Ken. Madelung Fluid Model for the Most Likely Wavefunction of a Single Free Particle In Two Dimensional Space with a Given Average Energy (2018) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0902.3838.pdf>
2. Ruggeri, Francesco. R Link Between Classical Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics for the Ground State of the Oscillator? (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
3. Perelman, Carlos Castro. Bohm's Potential classical/quantum duality and repulsive gravity (Phys. Letters B, 2019)
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physletb.2018.11.013>
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0370269318308517>
4. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Logarithm of Wavefunction as Partition Function? (preprint, zenodo, 2018)